

IMPROVING BLAST RESISTANCE OF HIGHWAY BRIDGE BY USING FRP

Yuxin Pan¹, Moe M. S. Cheung^{1*}

¹Western China Earthquake and Hazards Mitigation Research Centre, Sichuan University, Chengdu, China

* Corresponding author (mscheung@ust.hk)

Keywords: *CFRP, Blast load, Girder Bridges, Blast-resistance and Protection*

1 Introduction

During the whole service life of a bridge, it may suffer various types of dynamic hazards, including the possible blast load due to the increasing terrorist attacks in recent years. Taking into consideration of the high vulnerability and potential societal and economic impacts of bridge collapse, it is necessary to investigate the dynamic behavior of various bridge types under blast load effects, and further propose effective measurements for bridge protection.

Over the past few years, several codes and standards have provided information about blast-resist design, and prevention of progressive collapse has been an important consideration. Previously, both official and non-governmental design guidelines for military structures and buildings to resist weapons or blasting effects have been proposed, such as, “Design of Structures to Resist Nuclear Weapons Effects” [1], “Structural Design for Physical Security: State of Practice” [2] and US Army “Structures to resist the effects of accidental explosions” [3]. Although some of the developments could be applied on bridges, specific information on blast-resistant bridge design is still not widely available.

In 2003, American Association of State Highway and Officials (AASHTO) [4] have provided several suggestions to enhance blast-resistance of bridge structures that fall under two categories: modifications in the design stages and strengthening techniques on existing bridges. Since the adjustment on bridge design guidelines is a complicated and systematic task that requires long-term investigation, much extensive research has been conducted on strengthening techniques. These techniques can be concluded as: 1) provision of physical protection to reduce the direct blast impact on the structure, and 2) enhance the structure strength so that members

are able to withstand the energy from the attack. Among these measures, FRP reinforcement was expected as an effective way. However, over the past years, extensive military testing has been conducted to investigate the concrete structural response under various detonation scenarios, but little information was released in the open literature about the FRP protection. And the available documents, such as UFC 3-340-02 [3], were more focusing on structural design rather than strengthening the existing structures.

With the development of composite materials in past several decades, fiber reinforced polymers (FRP) have been widely used in structural design and building construction to enhance the structural performance and load bearing capacity, as well as the seismic resistance of shear walls, columns and structural joints [5]. Different types of fibres have been produced in the past years including carbon fibres (CFRP), glass fibres (GFRP) and Kevlar fibres (KFRP) all of which are available in various grades and types for different applications. In the structural engineering field, they are commonly used in application such as prestressing tendons for concrete and structural FRP wraps for repair and strengthening of reinforced concrete beams and columns. The results have demonstrated that FRP composites have potentials of becoming a practical and effective way of reinforcing concrete structures. FRP composites contain thin reinforcing fibres embedded in a resin matrix which can be classified as either polymer or epoxy matrix. The main uses of FRP composites in structural engineering field are: (1) enhancing their flexural strength and ductility, (2) strengthening material to structural component to withstand unexpected loads and (3) damage repair of structures.

In recent years, because of its thinness, high strength and high energy-absorption, both the experimental

and numerical studies of FRP reinforcement for building blast-resistant design have been investigated. However, no definite conclusions were made due to its complex failure mechanism and bonding conditions in resisting violent blast load. From the wave propagation point of view, even though the FRP wrapping of structural components will increase its strength, it may still cause multiple interfaces of blast wave reflection [6]. Due to the high level of applied pressure from a blasting event, the ductility of a structure will be reduced, but it is still unknown what level of the ductility reduction is. The performance of FRP composite is also highly dependent on the quality of the bond between resin and fibre layers. This governs the shear stress development in the matrix between individual fibres of the FRP system when subjected to impact loads. Limited studies have been conducted to examine the suitability of externally bonded FRP in enhancing the blast-resistance of concrete and masonry structures. In 1977, Crawford et al. [7] studied the effectiveness of FRP jacketing by using the computer program DYNA-3D, concluding that FRP strengthening could increase the structural performance of reducing fragmentation and projectiles formation, and near 50 to 60% of displacement could be reduced. Similar experimental testings on structural components were also carried out. Ross et al. [8] investigated the suitability of carbon fiber reinforced polymers (CFRP) as a blast resistance enhancing material in reinforced concrete beams. In 1995, the air blast tests on concrete masonry walls were performed by Muszynski [9]. It was reported that compared with the un-protected one, the structure that was partially strengthened with aramid (Kevlar) composites experienced a more ductile failure mode. Similarly, a somewhat relevant study was conducted by researchers at Wilfred Baker Engineering [10]. By bonding with Kevlar fabric (KFRP) on two faces, the out-of-plane bending resistance of 2.5m by 2.5m concrete masonry unit walls was enhanced significantly. Both the bending failure and shear failure were controlled with FRP strengthening. More recently, the blast response and ultimate resistance of RC slabs externally strengthened with CFRP laminates were investigated by Razaqpur et al. [11]. It was found that overall, the retrofitted slabs performed better than the control slabs, but one retrofitted slab completely failed under the blast load

while none of the control slabs experienced complete failure under similar load.

These studies, and other similar ones that have not been cited here, have provided comprehensive information of externally bonded FRP in increasing the blast-resistance of structural components or buildings. Based on the discussions above, one can see that it is a complex and challenging area of FRP strengthening under blast load. However, limited information was given on bridge structures, especially for highway bridges and long-span bridges. Therefore, the objective of this paper is to study the application of FRP on a concrete-steel composite slab-on-girder bridge to resist blast loads. Among various types of polymer materials, CFRP composite is selected in this study considering its high modulus of elasticity and low mass density. The CFRP material is represented by a homogenized orthotropic material, obtaining from experimental tests and numerical simulation [12]. A three-dimensional finite element model for girder bridge was built using a commercial explicit finite element package AUTODYN [13]. The CFRP laminates were implemented onto different locations of the bridge, with changing dimensions. Detailed bridge responses were observed and discussed in this paper, and several general comments were also given.

2 Basics of structural response under blast load

Normally, the detonation of high explosive immediately generates a spherical shock wave with high transient pressure that decays to atmospheric pressure level with increasing time and distance in a short period. A typical pressure-time history profile is presented in Fig. 1 and expressed by an exponential equation as shown below [14].

$$\Delta P(t) = P_s (1 - t/t_+) \exp\{-\alpha t/t_+\} \quad (1)$$

where P_s is the peak overpressure, t_+ is the duration of the positive phase and α is referred to a decay coefficient.

Both decoupled and fully coupled approaches have been proposed and used to predict structural response under blast load. Conventional structural nonlinear analysis for reinforced concrete structures under blast load is based on simplified decoupled approaches, either employing empirical formulas or assuming simplified triangle load pattern for estimation. With the rapid development of computer hardware and maturity of computational mechanics

over the last decades, it has become possible to conduct detailed numerical simulations of blasting effects on structures in personal computers. Among these methods, a fully coupled fluid-structure interaction model based on a coupled Euler-Lagrange finite element algorithm [15] has been identified as one of the most effective tools in blasting study. In order to solve the element number constraints and limitation of computational resources in conducting bridge structures simulation on personal computers, a Multi-Euler domain method [16] has been developed and was adopted in this study. The detailed procedure of the Multi-Euler domain method is summarized in the flowchart, as shown in Fig. 2 [17].

3 Computational models

3.1 Bridge configuration

As the most common types of bridge structures in highway systems, the reinforced concrete composite slab-on-girder bridge has been suffering many terrorist attacks during the past several decades. Therefore, in this study, it was chosen for the blasting analysis with detailed dimensions and appropriate material models. Fig. 3 presents the configurations and cross section dimensions of this bridge model. The bridge deck has two layers of steel reinforcements and the five steel girders are equally spaced at 2m apart.

3.2 Numerical material modeling & FEM techniques

The materials adopted in this study include concrete, steel, air, high explosive TNT and CFRP. For single span slab bridge, as illustrated in Fig. 3, a discrete model is employed to model the reinforced concrete deck, where the concrete and steel reinforcement are modeled with 8-node solid Lagrange element and 3-node Belytschko beam element, respectively. A perfect bond assumption is made so that the bond slip between the concrete and reinforcement is fully dependent on the concrete element only. A piecewise Drucker-Prager model is employed in representing the strength definition of concrete because the chosen strength model has been proven to be accurate in predicting the concrete behavior under both simple static tests and in the blast loading condition [18]. Because of the complex nonlinearity

of the macroscopic concrete, the Riedel-Hiermaier-Thoma (RHT) concrete failure model and the Porous equation of state (EOS) model [19] are used to consider the large-scale heterogeneity and porosity of concrete material under blast load. In this study, the Johnson and Cook material model [20] is used for all the steel components, including steel reinforcements and steel girders. The advantage of this model is that it allows users to define the stress strain curve arbitrarily in terms of the strain rate effect.

For the current study, the generation of blast loading relies on the remapping technology [13], where the high explosive is detonated and blast wave spreads in the air via a 1-D Arbitrary Lagrange-Euler (ALE) solver, and then the 1-D analysis result file would be imported into 3-D structural model for further coupled calculation by using the Multi-Euler domain method. The high explosive material and ambient air are modeled with the Jones-Wilkins-Lee (JWL) EOS and Ideal Gas EOS, respectively. All the air range surfaces have a boundary condition named the flow-out boundary condition to model the real infinite non-reflected air situation.

Among various types of CFRP models, the material properties adopted here are those developed and validated by comparing numerical simulations and impact experiments [12], as seen in Table 1. The modeling approach selected in this study incorporates a 3-D 8-node solid Lagrange element. Even though many researchers have conducted numerical simulation by using shell element to model CFRP under impact and blast loads, considering its better computational efficiency, this application would not allow the accurate prediction of shock waves propagating through the thickness of the laminate. The CFRP laminates is represented by a homogenized orthotropic EOS, orthotropic yield strength model and orthotropic softening failure model. Understanding the fact that debonding is one of the primary failure modes of FRP protection under blast loads, proper modeling of the interface between structures and FRP laminate is a considerable challenge. However, in order to save the computational resources in this study, the perfect bond assumption is introduced in interface modeling since the simulation duration is relatively small (millisecond level), and normally under dynamic load, the failure mostly occurs inside the concrete layers [21].

Generally, the accuracy of the explicit finite element analysis is highly affected by the mesh size, and a small mesh size normally is required to ensure a reliable structural performance under blast loads. However, due to the limitation of the computational resources and the limited field of a typical blast event, it is impractical to model all the bridge components with small mesh size. Convergence studies have been conducted and it was found that a 10cm mesh size was adequate to ensure a reliable pressure time-history and dynamic structural response compared with the experimental data.

4 Numerical analysis and result discussion

Based on the existing failure records of bridges subjected to blast load, it can be concluded that terrorist attacks are highly unpredictable events. Many factors, such as the TNT charge weights, detonation locations and standoff distances, would result in different structural responses for each particular case. However, this study focuses on the strengthening techniques to increase the capacity of the bridge against blast load. Therefore, a critical blasting event is needed, rather than investigating all the possibilities. Among various possible blasting attacks towards this highway bridge structure, the below-deck detonation of 100kg equivalent TNT is assumed as the worst case scenario, since many researchers have concluded that due to the complex wave reflection and confinement effect, an explosion occurs beneath a bridge will lead to the most severe damage [17, 22]. Hence, the blasting scenario selected in this study is a hand-placed detonation at a close distance below the bridge deck. Moreover, since the design codes for bridges have not incorporated the basic capacity to endure upward bending moments and shear, and the conventional bridge itself was designed with certain redundancy to withstand dead load and vehicle load only, a hand-placed charge near the steel girders may generate a large upward dynamic force that will cause an unusual structural response of the bridge. In the meantime, the separation of the girder system and the large bending appeared in steel girders will definitely make the situation much more severe. Fig. 4 presents this most vulnerable detonation event. To simplify the analysis, a half bridge model was built taking the mid-span as the symmetry axis and the total calculation time is 6.5ms.

4.1 Bridge performance without CFRP protection

Fig. 5(a) shows the propagation of air pressure using the Multi-Euler domain method. The light-colored surfaces in the air zone represent the incident blast waves and the gauges in the air were used to record the high blast pressure and impulse at different locations. As shown in the pressure time-history profile in Fig. 5(b), the pressure at Gauge 16 (4m away from the detonation centre) has been amplified nearly 50% compared with that at Gauge 10 (2m away from the detonation centre), demonstrating the complex reflected pressure phenomenon and the confinement effect involved in this case.

Response of the slab bridge without CFRP protection subjected to 100kg TNT below-deck explosion is calculated. Fig. 6(a) shows the damage propagation of bridge deck at different time instants. As the blast pressure is mainly limited between the 2nd and 3rd girder along the longitudinal direction, it can be seen clearly due to the half confinement effect and the reflected pressure, more than 1/3 of the area of the concrete deck suffers severe damage, and the whole segmentation between the 2nd and 3rd girder fails completely. Additionally, because of the direct uplift force and the horizontal deformation of steel girders created by the blast loads, the separations of the girder system are also captured, as seen in Fig. 6(b). The highly localized crushing of concrete elements resulted from the half confined explosion have had a significant effect on the overall bridge stability. For steel girder, compared with the 301.9mm of vertical deformation appeared in concrete deck, only a 88mm of horizontal deformation was generated without obvious failure, indicating the good ductility and high strength of steel material in resisting blast load.

4.2 Bridge performance under CFRP strengthening

In order to investigate the effectiveness of CFRP strengthening in blast-resistant design, 2m*4m range of CFRP sheet with 5mm thick was bonded to the bottom (front surface) and the top (backside) of the bridge deck, respectively. Fig. 7 shows the damage states of the two strengthening bridge deck at 3.5ms and 6.5ms. Comparing with unprotected case, shown in Fig. 6(a), only the damaged areas at two fixed end were reduced marginally, indicating this localized protection does not significantly improve the blast

resistance of the bridge subjected to 100kg TNT explosion. However, it should be noted that, at the early stage of the explosion (within 3.5ms), less damaged concrete were produced in upper deck protection case, proving the effectiveness of CFRP at backside in reducing the fragmentation and projectiles formation.

Similar results could also be found in displacement comparison. The maximum vertical displacements on bridge deck with CFRP strengthening at backside are 164.9mm at 3.5ms and 304.6mm at 6.5ms, respectively, which are similar to the un-protected case that are 161.3mm and 301.9mm. However, larger displacements (180.8mm and 340.7mm) are observed from the front-surface strengthening case, which could be explained by that under the FRP strengthening at front surface, multiple interfaces of blast wave propagation were generated resulting in much stronger wave reflection.

In order to study the dynamic response of the bridge under externally bonded CFRP, a virtual gauge was set on the concrete deck right above the detonation center to capture the vertical velocity time-history. It can be observed from Fig. 8 that at the initial stage, both the two protected bridge decks produced a higher vertical velocity compared with the bridge without CFRP reinforcement. From the wave propagation point of view, as reviewed before, CFRP may create multiple interfaces of blast wave reflection and consequently it may cause velocity variations under direct wave shock. With the wave propagation, strengthening decreased the dynamic response of the deck eventually. Overall the strengthened bridge performed better than the original one, but the improvement is insignificant. This observation is consistent with other researchers' conclusions that 1) the reinforcement should be installed in the backside of the structure, rather than the front surface [23]; and 2) a single side protection may contribute very little to blast-resistance of structures [24].

To further study the bridge performance subjected to blast load by using CFRP, three more cases are conducted, including two back side CFRP strengthened cases with larger (4m*12m) and full (10m*24m) reinforcements and one full protected case that using CFRP bonded on both sides of the deck. Unfortunately, compared with the un-reinforced bridge model, equal damaged states are produced in these three protected cases even where

more polymer materials have been adopted, demonstrating that the RC slab-on-girder bridge chosen in this study could not withstand the shock waves resulting from the explosion of 100kg of TNT below-deck detonations at close standoff distance. However, it still can be observed that both the three larger CFRP strengthening and the unprotected case generated almost the same peak values of vertical velocity within 3ms, but decayed into different ultimate states (20m/s, 30m/s and 50m/s), demonstrating the effectiveness of CFRP in stabilizing the bridge dynamic response, as seen in Fig. 9. Similar results could also be found in displacement comparison. Compared with the un/small-reinforced cases, the maximum vertical deformations of three CFRP strengthened cases are 286.3mm, 270.9mm and 240.8mm, respectively, indicating the remarkable capacity of larger CFRP laminates in reducing the deck deformation, especially the strengthening at both sides,

5 Conclusions

This paper studied the structural responses of a CFRP strengthened RC highway bridge subjected to blast loads. By using the Multi-Euler domain method, the numerical analysis of full-scale bridges was conducted on personal computers with high efficiency and accuracy. Findings and comments obtained from the study are as follows:

- (1) Numerical results show that for the adopted bridge model, damage is mainly induced by wave propagation with concrete spalling and crushing, especially if explosion is set very close to the girder system. Due to the close standoff distance and the confinement effects involved, an under-deck detonation with 100kg equivalent TNT has been identified as the most critical case
- (2) In order to study the effectiveness of FRP in improving the blast-resistance of the bridge, the 5mm thick CFRP reinforcement with different dimensions was applied on either the compressive and tensile side of the concrete deck, respectively. Numerical results indicate that overall the strengthened bridge performed better than the original one, but the improvement is insignificant. Additionally, the reinforcement should be installed in the backside of the structure, rather than the front surface, since CFRP protection is more effective in

reducing the fragmentation and projectiles formation, rather than enhancing the structural strength.

(3) Parametric study also shows that the bridge performed better with larger area of CFRP strengthening, especially installment on both sides of the bridge deck, even though the damage reduction is relatively small, demonstrating the vulnerability of the slab-on-girder bridge itself in resisting 100kg TNT. Therefore, it is difficult to come up with definite conclusions about the blast mitigation capacity of CFRP. Further field testing and analysis of using FRP strengthening are needed.

References

- [1] ASCE *Design of Structures to Resist Nuclear Weapons Effects*, Manual 42, American Society of Civil Engineering, Washington, D.C., 1985.
- [2] EJ. Conrath, T. Krauthammer, KA. Marchand and PF. Alakar *Structural Design of Physical Security: State of Practice*. ASCE: Reston, VA, 1999.
- [3] Unified Facilities Criteria (UFC) 3-340-02 *Structures to resist the effects of accidental explosions*. U.S. Department of the Army, Navy and Air Force Technical Manual, 2008.
- [4] American Association of State Highway and Officials (AASHTO) *Load and Resistant Factor Design, Bridge Design Specifications*, 2003.
- [5] M. Engindeniz, LF. Kahn and AH. Zureick "Repair and Strengthening of Beam-Column Joints: State-of-the-Art". *ACI Structural Journal*, 102(2), 1-14, 2005.
- [6] JM. Biggs *Introduction to structural dynamics*. McGraw-Hill, New York, 1964.
- [7] JE. Crawford, LI. Malvar, IW. Wesevich, I. Valancius and A. Reynolds "Retrofit of reinforced concrete structures to resist blast effects". *ACI Struct J*:94(4):371-7. 1977.
- [8] CA. Ross, MR. Purcell and EL. Jerome "Blast response of concrete beams and slabs externally reinforced with fibre reinforced plastics (FRP)". In: *Proceedings of the struct cong XV-building to last*, Portland, USA; April 1997. p. 673-7. 1997.
- [9] LC. Muszynski "Explosive field tests to evaluate composite reinforcement of concrete masonry walls". *Proceedings of ICCI'98*; 1998. p. 276-84. 1998.
- [10] Wilfred Baker Engineering, 2000. Private communication, 2001.
- [11] AG. Razaqpur, E. Contestabile and A. Tolba "Experimental study of the strength and deformations of carbon fibre reinforced polymer (CFRP) retrofitted reinforced concrete slabs under blast". *Canadian Journal of Civil Engineering*, 36: 1366-1377, 2009.
- [12] M. Wicklein, S. Ryan, DM. White and RA. Clegg "Hypervelocity impact on CFRP: Testing, material modeling, and numerical simulation". *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 35: 181-1869, 2008.
- [13] AUTODYN *Remapping Tutorial, revision 4.3*, Century Dynamics, 2005.
- [14] G. Kinney and K. Graham *Explosive shocks in air. 2nd*, Springer, New York, 1985.
- [15] NK. Birnbaum, NJ. Francis and BI. Gerber "Coupled techniques for the simulation of Fluid-Structure and Impact Problems". *Computer Assisted Mechanics and Engineering Sciences*, vol. 6, n. 3-4, pp. 295-311, 1999.
- [16] YX. Pan, YB. Chan and MS. Cheung "Blast loading effects on an RC slab-on-girder bridge superstructure using the Multi-Euler domain method". *ASCE's Journal of Bridge Engineering*, accepted on Dec 12, 2012.
- [17] YX. Pan *Blast load effects on bridges using the Multi-Euler domain method*, MPhil Thesis, HKUST, Hong Kong, 2012.
- [18] XQ. Zhou, VA. Kuznetsov, H. Hao and J. Waschl "Numerical prediction of concrete slab response to blast loading". *International Journal of Impact Engineering*, 35: 1186-1200, 2008.
- [19] W. Riedel, K. Thoma, S. Hiermaier and E. Schmolinske "Penetrating of reinforced concrete by EBTA-B-500 numerical analysis using a new macroscopic concrete model for hydrocodes". In: *Proceedings of ninth international symposium of IEMS*, Berlin, 315-22, 1999.
- [20] GR. Johnson and WH. Cook "A constitutive model and data for metals subjected to large strains, high strain rates and high temperatures". *Proceedings of the 7th international symposium on ballistics*, Hague, Netherlands, p: 541-548, 1983.
- [21] XQ. Li, ZJ. Yang, JF. Chen and Y. Lu "Loading Rate Effect on FRP-to-Concrete Bond Behavior". *Advanced Materials Research*, Vol. 250-253, 3571-3576, 2011.
- [22] DG. Winget, KA. Marchand and EB. Williamson "Analysis and Design of Critical Bridges Subjected to Blast Loads". *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 131(8), 1243-1255, 2005.
- [23] M. Irshidat, A. Al-Ostaz, AHD. Cheng and C. Mullen "Nanoparticle reinforced polymer for blast protection of unreinforced masonry wall: Laboratory blast load simulation and design models". *Journal of Structural Engineering*, 137(10), 1193-1204, 2011.
- [24] PE. Silva and B. Lu "Improving the blast resistance capacity of RC slabs with innovative composites materials". *Compos Part B: Eng* 38:523-534, 2006.

Table 1. Data set of the CFRP orthotropic EOS model

Reference Density	1.563	Bulk Modulus A_1	25.04
Young's Modulus 11	72.90	Parameter A_2	0
Young's Modulus 22	22.89	Parameter A_3	0
Young's Modulus 33	9.07	Parameter B_0	1.098
Poisson's Ratio 12	0.77	Parameter B_1	1.098
Poisson's Ratio 23	0.55	Parameter T_1	25.04
Poisson's Ratio 31	0.019	Parameter T_1	0
Shear Modulus 12	48.35		
Shear Modulus 23	0.558		
Shear Modulus 31	0.873		

Fig. 3 Slab-on-girder bridge model

Fig. 4 Blasting scenario for girder bridge

Fig. 1 Typical blast pressure-time history

Fig. 2 Flowchart of the Multi-Euler domain method

(a) Wave propagation

(b) Pressure time-histories of Gauge 10&16

Fig. 5 Blast wave spread for below-deck with 100kg TNT detonation

(a) Damage of bridge deck without CFRP protection

(b) Separation of girder system

Fig. 6 Dynamic response of the un-protected bridge

Fig. 8 Velocity comparison for front and back CFRP protections

Fig. 9 Velocity comparison for four CFRP backside reinforced cases

Fig. 7 Damage of CFRP strengthened concrete deck (top face)